

THE EFFECTS OF METACOGNITIVE STRATEGIES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY IN EFL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study was quasi-experimental with a pre-test and post-test with a control group to evaluate the effect of metacognitive strategies on creativity among EFL students. The statistical population consisted of 70 EFL students who were randomly selected through multi-stage cluster sampling (Creswell, 2014). Data were collected using the Torrance Creativity Questionnaire, a well-established instrument for assessing creativity, which has demonstrated reliability in various contexts (Torrance, 1990). The reliability based on Cronbach's alpha coefficient, was 0.76 for creativity. Data analysis from the tests was conducted using SPSS22 software. The results of the study indicated that the using of metacognitive strategies had a positive and significant effect on the development of creativity in EFL students. The results underscore the potential of incorporating such strategies into language learning curricula to improve creativity and academic outcomes.

Keywords: Metacognitive Strategies, Creativity, EFL Learner

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most distinguishing characteristics of human beings, essential for the continuity of life, is the power of thought. However, a concerning deficiency observed in many students and later in adults is their difficulty in articulating ideas, solving problems, and innovating. While humans have always possessed the capacity for thought, enabling them creativity is crucial for personal growth and development. Since creativity represent some of the most intricate and advanced forms of human thought, it is vital for students, particularly English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners, to be exposed to and accustomed to beautiful ideas.

Evidence suggests that when cognitive and metacognitive concepts are clearly articulated and taught, there is a marked improvement in fostering a creative generation equipped with strong problem-solving skills across various educational domains. This enhancement, in turn, boosts students' self-esteem and academic self-concept.

These ideas resonate with the perspectives of many education experts, advocating for active learning instead of passive absorption, recognizing individual differences, and appreciating students as multifaceted individuals. Often, students attempt to follow lessons without fully comprehending the material, struggling to articulate their problem-solving processes or to innovate. Interestingly, direct instruction in metacognitive strategies may yield positive outcomes, as teaching strategies can lead to enhanced performance. Therefore, this research aimed to explore the impact of metacognitive strategies on the creativity of EFL

learners, focusing on how these strategies can cultivate their innovative capacities.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Creativity is a hallmark of humanity, respected across various fields such as science, art, literature, and culture. Nurturing creativity should therefore be a primary educational objective (Dosumbekova, 2024). Experts today view creativity as a crucial element for driving change and innovation, significantly influencing human scientific and technological advancements. Research indicates that the future of innovation will hinge on the extent to which creativity is fostered and utilized (Benjamin & McLean, 2022). Although creativity is an inherent trait present from childhood, it requires attention and guidance to develop fully (Chen et al., 2023). Childhood is particularly important for cultivating creativity, as children need ample opportunities to gain experiences that enrich their creative potential. Creativity is not only vital in childhood; it is a lifelong necessity (Ismiyati, 2014). Essentially, creativity involves generating suitable solutions to problems, demonstrating innovative behavior in response to challenges (Pachler et al., 2019). Divergent thinking, which seeks unconventional solutions, is crucial for fostering creativity (Yildirim, 2010). Creativity plays a pivotal role in individual and collective human advancement, as all human inventions and achievements stem from creative thought. Research indicates that appropriate methodologies can nurture creativity, with teaching metacognitive strategies emerging as one effective approach (Rafiei & Mousavi Fard, 2023).

Metacognitive strategies can significantly influence creativity, as metacognitive thinking is crucial for improving academic performance (Nordahl et al., 2020). Simply amassing knowledge is insufficient; instead, learners must engage in self-awareness, control, and monitoring of their learning processes, which are fundamental aspects of metacognition (Nilson & Zimmerman, 2013). Many learners encounter difficulties in scientific reasoning due to a lack of metacognitive skills, often stemming from their educational experiences (Güner & Erbay, 2021). Research indicates that study programs, learning strategies, and the evaluation of these strategies play crucial roles in effective learning (Theobald, 2021). Educational experts argue that successful learning is linked to developing metacognitive knowledge, enabling students to become more independent in their learning (Razmjooei et al., 2023). Engaging students in metacognitive processes, such as planning, monitoring, and reflecting on their thinking, leads to effective learning outcomes. Researchers contend that these metacognitive skills can be taught and integrated into the curriculum for greater benefits (Bae & Kwon, 2021). However, current educational curricula often overlook metacognitive components (Termaat, 2024).

Research indicates that metacognitive skills significantly contribute to students' development of study strategies and improvement in classroom performance. These skills enable learners to assess their prior knowledge, monitor their understanding, and modify their comprehension during the learning process. Some studies suggest that metacognitive strategies account for up to 70% of students' academic performance (Celik, 2022). Metacognitive strategies are considered essential components of effective learning strategies, encompassing two main elements: first, learners' awareness of the nature of the learning task and its requirements, and second, their possession of the necessary knowledge to complete that task. Consequently, individuals who utilize metacognitive strategies are better equipped with both new information and cognitive techniques (Rivas et al., 2022).

Metacognitive training promotes an active learning approach, highlighting the importance of strategies and cognitive processes. Through this training, learners realize the significance of emphasizing key points, ultimately enhancing their learning efficiency. This educational approach involves guidance and monitoring of activities and cognitive processes. It is crucial to view metacognition not as an end goal but as a means to empower learners with the knowledge and skills necessary to manage their learning effectively, fostering curiosity and skillfulness in future tasks (Hamidi et al., 2024).

In recent years, there has been a surge in scientific research focused on creativity, innovation, and effectiveness, driven by the growing importance of these issues. Creativity is a universal ability shaped by individual, personality, and social factors. Although the capacity for creative thinking is inherent in all humans, its development requires cultivation. Schools play a vital role in nurturing creativity, as the socialization process begins when children enter educational environments. However, various factors, such as excessive assignments, an emphasis on rote memorization, rigid programs, and neglect of individual differences, can hinder the creative potential of children. If schools adopt conditions and teaching methods that incorporate metacognitive strategies and practical approaches to creativity, they can enhance students' creative abilities and improve their academic self-concept (Farazandeh et al., 2022).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent advancements in human life can largely be attributed to creativity and innovation. A key component in fostering creative thinking is education, which aims to nurture innovative individuals. When learners have opportunities to express their thoughts and participate in decision-making processes that influence their lives, they tend to exhibit greater creativity and assume more responsibility. Thus, emphasizing education during early childhood is essential for cultivating creativity in children (Nikkola et al., 2022).

In recent years, the concept of "creativity" has gained increased attention within modern educational literature. Many experts and educators have recognized that students, particularly EFL learners, often struggle with analytical skills and creative thinking, typically sticking to conventional approaches when confronted with new challenges. This rigid adherence to learned frameworks can hinder their ability to think creatively, particularly when faced with unfamiliar situations (Martínez-Otero, 2021).

Progressive educational systems now advocate for the practice of "unlearning," encouraging students to break free from rigid thought patterns. In these systems, learners are encouraged to move beyond past knowledge and understand that true learning involves creativity and the reinterpretation of what they have learned (Soleimani, 2021).

The elementary education system plays a pivotal role in shaping students' creative potential. Therefore, it is crucial to design curricula that reflect the rapidly changing modern world. In addition to traditional educational goals, contemporary curricula must integrate new objectives to nurture creativity. Children's innate creative potential often emerges from their genuine desire to express themselves. Thus, integrating creativity into the elementary curriculum can foster personal development, self-confidence, and psychological well-being (Brovchak et al., 2024).

Research shows that while most children initially display high levels of creativity, this often declines around the age of ten. This decline is linked to ineffective teaching methods that fail to promote creative thinking (Larysa et al., 2020). According to studies, while 98% of children exhibit creativity, much of it diminishes as they enter school, resulting in reduced engagement in learning and increased behavioral issues. Eisner's critique of contemporary education emphasizes that schools tend to focus solely on knowledge acquisition, neglecting the creative skills essential for a holistic education (Tan, 2021).

Several studies highlight the positive influence of metacognitive strategies on the creativity of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. (Rahmati, 2024) explored the impact of computer skills training on various skills among primary school students in Tehran and found that structured training significantly boosted creativity. Similarly, (Orakci & Durnali, 2023) demonstrated that enhancing teachers' metacognitive knowledge led to improved academic performance and creativity in elementary students, indicating that teacher training in metacognitive strategies can directly benefit students' creative abilities.

(Hayat et al., 2020) also showed that teaching metacognitive strategies significantly enhanced creativity and academic performance among middle school students. Their research underscored the importance of these strategies in increasing students' self-efficacy and emotional engagement in learning. In another study, (Maor et al., 2023) found a notable positive correlation between metacognitive skills and students' creativity, suggesting that strong metacognitive awareness can lead to improved creative thinking.

Furthermore, (Dilekçi & Karatay, 2023) examined the impact of a 21st-century skills curriculum, which incorporated metacognitive strategies, on students' creative thinking skills. Their results indicated significant improvements in creativity alongside enhanced willingness to engage in learning.

(Carvalho & Santos, 2022) highlighted the role of a peer learning program that utilized advanced technology to develop metacognitive skills among educators, which in turn facilitated their capacity to foster creativity in EFL learners.

Collectively, these studies affirm that integrating metacognitive strategies into teaching methodologies significantly enhances the creativity of EFL learners, promoting their overall academic performance and engagement.

RQ

What is the impact of metacognitive strategies on the creativity of EFL students?

RH

Metacognitive strategies have a significant impact on the creativity of EFL students.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a semi-experimental design for data collection, utilized a pre-test and post-test approach with both an experimental and a control group.

3.1. Sample

This study employed cluster random sampling due to the unavailability of a complete list of individuals in the population. A creativity questionnaire was administered to fifth-grade students, leading to the selection of 70 students with low creativity scores for further analysis. These students were then randomly assigned to either the experimental or control group.

Torrance Creativity Questionnaire: This instrument includes 60 multiple-choice questions, categorized into four subtests: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. Responses reflect varying levels of creativity, scored from 1 (low) to 3 (high). The total score for each participant ranges from 60 to 180, representing their overall creativity. The questionnaire's validity was established in Iran by (Rezaei et al., 2020), demonstrating strong construct validity through factor analysis and reliability indicated by a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.84.

3.2. Creativity Questionnaire

While the standard creativity questionnaire maintained its content validity, minor adjustments were made for alignment with the statistical population. Specialists and educators in educational sciences and management confirmed its content and face validity. Factor analysis yielded 60 suitable items, capturing 62% of the variance, with a KMO test score of 0.705 and significant results from Bartlett's test ($P < 0.000$), validating the sample size and the existence of these factors within the population.

3.3. Procedure

Following preparations, the pre-test was administered to the research groups. After ensuring the equivalence of participants, they were randomly allocated to the experimental and control groups. Ethical considerations were upheld by obtaining consent forms and coding participants to protect their confidentiality.

In this step, the metacognitive strategies training based on (Greif et al., 2020) was implemented. The experimental group participated in eight 60-minute sessions focused on enhancing metacognitive skills, while the control group received no intervention during this period.

Table 3.1: the Content of Metacognitive Learning Strategies Intervention

Session Description	Sessions
Introduced the training, created motivation, established interaction, and articulated the goals and significance of metacognitive skill development	1
Explained metacognitive strategies, emphasizing their role in enhancing awareness of cognitive skills and appropriate responses in various situations	2
Covered planning strategies: goal-setting and predicting the necessary time and pace, comparing planning to a football coach's strategy adjustments	3
expanded on planning strategies: focused attention and readiness to apply learning strategies, encouraging students to select a topic and appropriate strategy for behavioral improvement	4
Introduced monitoring control strategies, encouraging learners to reflect on their actions, recognize issues, and evaluate their understanding through self-questioning	5
Discussed additional control and monitoring strategies, focusing on adjusting reaction times to social situations	6
taught organizational strategies: modifying cognitive strategies to enhance social development when previous approaches were unsuccessful	7
Reviewed the content collectively, addressed issues, and assigned a group project focused on presenting suitable metacognitive strategies for a social challenge	8

4. DATA ANALYSIS

The results were analyzed using SPSS22 software, employing both descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics through analysis of covariance tests. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was applied to assess data normality.

Table 4.1. The descriptive indices of research variables

Variable	Group	Stage	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosi
Creativity	EX	PRE	35	1.60	0.34	0.25	1.12
		POST	35	3.92	0.41	0.03	0.42
Creativity	CONTRL	PRE	35	1.80	0.42	0.04	0.31
		POST	35	1.78	0.43	0.14	0.16

Table 4.2. The result of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the normality of data distribution

Variable	Group	Stage	Count	z-value	p-value		Result
Creativity	EX	PRE	35	1.06	0.20		Normal
		POST	35	1.14	0.13		Normal
Creativity	CONTRL	PRE	35	1.03	0.23		Normal
		POST	35	0.92	0.34		Normal

The analysis presented in Table 3.3 indicated that the preliminary assessment for homogeneity of regression slopes demonstrates no significant interaction between the covariate (pre-test) and the group factor. As a result, the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances are satisfied, fulfilling the conditions necessary for conducting an analysis of covariance (ANCOVA).

Research Hypothesis: Metacognitive strategies significantly enhance the creativity of fifth-grade EFL learners.

Table4.3. Results of Homogeneity of Regression Slopes Test

Source	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F-Value	Significance Level
Group / Creativity Pre-test	1	0.26	4.63	0.24	

Based on the results of Table 3.4, the preliminary analysis to assess the homogeneity of slopes shows that the interaction effect between the covariate (pre-test) and the factor is not significant. As a result, the assumptions of approximate normality and homogeneity of variances are met, and the necessary conditions for using the ANCOVA test are satisfied.

Table4.4: ANCOVA Results for Creativity in Experimental and Control Groups

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F-Value	Significance Level (p-value)	Eta Squared	Levene's Test
Creativity	0.01	1	0.05	0.81	0.001	0.07	0.78
Group	76.55	1	76.55	392.98	0.0001	0.85	
Error	13.05	1	67	0.19			
Total	670.47	1	70				

The ANCOVA results for creativity among EFL learners in both the experimental and control groups showed a significant effect (Eta = 0.85, P = 0.0001, F (1, 67) = 392.98), indicating a meaningful difference between the two groups. This suggested that metacognitive strategies positively influence creativity.

5. CONCLUSION

Previous studies, such as (May et al., 2020), have shown that training in metacognitive strategies for teachers enhances students' creativity. Similarly, (He et al., 2024) found that metacognitive strategy training positively impacts creativity and academic performance. These findings align with the present research, as reported by (Von Hoyer et al., 2022) confirm the beneficial relationship between metacognitive strategies and creative thinking. These outcomes suggest that equipping students with metacognitive strategies encourages deeper engagement with their subjects and fosters divergent thinking in problem-solving. Consequently, such training empowers students to gain greater control over their learning and facilitates the emergence of creative skills like flexibility, fluency, and originality.

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

-The study focused on fifth-grade EFL learners; therefore, generalizing the results to other cities or grade levels should be approached with caution.

-Due to challenges in accessing students, follow-up assessments could not be conducted within a designated timeframe.

- The brief duration of the intervention and time constraints limited the depth of content covered and sample size.

Practical Recommendations

-Educational district managers should organize training sessions for school counselors to enhance their knowledge of metacognitive strategies, thereby improving the quality of their support for students.

-Teachers should act as facilitators, guiding students on metacognitive strategies, allowing learners to take ownership of their educational processes.

-Educational psychology specialists should create environments that foster the teaching of metacognitive strategies to enhance students' creativity and skill development.

REFERENCE LIST

Bae, H., & Kwon, K. (2021). Developing metacognitive skills through class activities: what makes students use metacognitive skills? *Educational Studies*, 47(4), 456–471.

Benjamin, K. A., & McLean, S. (2022). Change the medium, change the message: creativity is key to battle

- misinformation. In *Advances in Physiology Education* (Vol. 46, Issue 2, pp. 259–267). American Physiological Society Rockville, MD.
- Brovchak, L. S., Starovoit, L. V, Likhitska, L. M., Todosiienko, N. L., & Shvets, I. B. (2024). Integrating music, drama and visual arts in extracurricular programs: enhancing psychological development in early school-aged children. *Sapienza: International Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 5(3), e24052–e24052.
- Carvalho, A. R., & Santos, C. (2022). Developing peer mentors' collaborative and metacognitive skills with a technology-enhanced peer learning program. *Computers and Education Open*, 3, 100070.
- Celik, B. (2022). The effect of metacognitive strategies on self-efficacy, motivation and academic achievement of university students. *Canadian Journal of Educational and Social Studies*, 2(4), 37–55.
- Chen, W., Wang, B., Chen, Y., Zhang, J., & Xiao, Y. (2023). New exploration of creativity: Cross-validation analysis of the factors influencing multiteam digital creativity in the transition phase. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1102085.
- Dilekçi, A., & Karatay, H. (2023). The effects of the 21st century skills curriculum on the development of students' creative thinking skills. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 47, 101229.
- Dosumbekova, F. (2024). *The Impact of Humanities: The intrinsic value of arts and culture in an analytically-driven world*.
- Farazandeh, F., Younesi, J., & Tarverdizadeh, H. (2022). Investigating the Effectiveness of Teaching (Cognitive and Meta-Cognitive) Learning Strategies in the Enhancement of Academic Vitality amongst Pre-University Students and Applied Sciences and Technology University Students from Tehran. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 9981–9992.
- Greif, R., Bhanji, F., Bigham, B. L., Bray, J., Breckwoldt, J., Cheng, A., Duff, J. P., Gilfoyle, E., Hsieh, M.-J., Iwami, T., & others. (2020). Education, implementation, and teams: 2020 international consensus on cardiopulmonary resuscitation and emergency cardiovascular care science with treatment recommendations. *Circulation*, 142(16_suppl_1), S222--S283.
- Güner, P., & Erbay, H. N. (2021). Metacognitive Skills and Problem-Solving. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 7(3), 715–734.
- Hamidi, F., Soleymani, S., Dazy, S., & Meshkat, M. (2024). Teaching Mathematics Based on Integrating Reading Strategies and Working Memory in Elementary School. *Athens Journal of Education*, 11(1), 9–22.
- Hayat, A. A., Shateri, K., Amini, M., & Shokrpour, N. (2020). Relationships between academic self-efficacy, learning-related emotions, and metacognitive learning strategies with academic performance in medical students: a structural equation model. *BMC Medical Education*, 20, 1–11.
- He, G., Chen, S., Lin, H., & Su, A. (2024). The association between initial metacognition and subsequent academic achievement: a meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Educational Psychology Review*, 36(3), 1–32.
- Ismiyati, E. D. (2014). *Developing Appropriate Activities For Children At Tpa Pelangi Nusa, Wates, Kulon Progo*. Yogyakarta State University.
- Larysa, Z., Galyna, B., Valentyna, G., Borys, A., & Liudmyla, P. (2020). Creativity formation in the context of social and psychological adaptation of preschoolers aged 5-6 Years. *International Journal of Cognitive Research in Science, Engineering and Education*, 8(S), 79–91.
- Maor, R., Paz-Baruch, N., Grinshpan, N., Milman, A., Mevarech, Z., Levi, R., Shlomo, S., & Zion, M. (2023). Relationships between metacognition, creativity, and critical thinking in self-reported teaching performances in project-based learning settings. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 50, 101425.
- Martínez-Otero, V. (2021). Coexistence in School: A Proposal for Preventing Violence. *Security in the Global Commons and Beyond*, 207–220.
- May, J., Redding, E., Whatley, S., Łuczniak, K., Clements, L., Weber, R., Sikorski, J., & Reed, S. (2020). Enhancing creativity by training metacognitive skills in mental imagery. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 38, 100739.

- Nikkola, T., Reunamo, J., & Ruokonen, I. (2022). Children's creative thinking abilities and social orientations in Finnish early childhood education and care. *Early Child Development and Care*, 192(6), 872–886.
- Nilson, L. B., & Zimmerman, B. J. (2013). *Creating self-regulated learners: Strategies to strengthen students' self-awareness and learning skills*. Routledge.
- Nordahl, K. B., Owen, M. T., Ribeiro, L. A., & Zachrisson, H. D. (2020). Parenting quality from observational ratings at age 2: Validation from Norwegian and US samples. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 53, 379–390.
- Orakci, \cSenol, & Durnali, M. (2023). The mediating effects of metacognition and creative thinking on the relationship between teachers' autonomy support and teachers' self-efficacy. *Psychology in the Schools*, 60(1), 162–181.
- Pachler, D., Kuonath, A., & Frey, D. (2019). How transformational lecturers promote students' engagement, creativity, and task performance: The mediating role of trust in lecturer and self-efficacy. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 69, 162–172.
- Rafiei, N., & Mousavi Fard, S. M. (2023). Effectiveness of Teaching Creative Thinking by De Bono Method on the Academic Self-concept and School Enthusiasm of Students with Dyslexia. *Journal of Exceptional Children*, 23(2), 91–104.
- Rahmati, P. (2024). *Exploring Teachers' Cognition and Practices of Pronunciation Instruction: The Impact of an Online Professional Development Program*. Oklahoma State University.
- Razmjooei, P., Zarei, R., Shahamat, N., & Salehi, M. (2023). Designing the Development a Model of Organizational Research Culture in Education (Subject of Study: Primary School Teachers of the Four Districts of Shiraz City). *Journal of Educational Sciences*, 30(1), 189–210.
- Rezaei, H., Saeed, A. F. M., Abdi, K., Ebadi, A., Ghanei Gheshlagh, R., & Kurdi, A. (2020). Translation and validation of the Farsi version of the pain management self-efficacy questionnaire. *Journal of Pain Research*, 719–727.
- Rivas, S. F., Saiz, C., & Ossa, C. (2022). Metacognitive strategies and development of critical thinking in higher education. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 913219.
- Soleimani, A. (2021). Identification and analysis of elements affecting the development of creative cities in Iranian metropolises (case study: Tabriz metropolis). *Physical Social Planning*, 8(1), 99–110.
- Tan, O.-S. (2021). *Problem-based learning innovation: Using problems to power learning in the 21st century*. Gale Cengage Learning.
- Termaat, A. (2024). How disciplinary detail obscures the metacognitive potential of curriculums. *Curriculum Perspectives*, 1–17.
- Theobald, M. (2021). Self-regulated learning training programs enhance university students' academic performance, self-regulated learning strategies, and motivation: A meta-analysis. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 66, 101976.
- Von Hoyer, J., Hoppe, A., Kammerer, Y., Otto, C., Pardi, G., Rokicki, M., Yu, R., Dietze, S., Ewerth, R., & Holtz, P. (2022). The search as learning spaceship: Toward a comprehensive model of psychological and technological facets of search as learning. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 827748.
- Yildirim, A. (2010). Creativity In Early Childhood Education Program. *Procedia-Social And Behavioral Sciences*, 9, 1561–1565.